

**PRINCIPALS' MANAGERIAL ROLES AS CORRELATES TO SCHOOL
PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR AN ENHANCED MANAGEMENT
TRAINING WORKSHOP**

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Principals' Managerial Roles as Correlates to School Performance: Basis for an Enhanced Management Training Workshop

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the principals' managerial roles as correlates to school performance which served as basis for an enhanced management training workshop during the school year 2023-2024. The perception of the two groups of respondents on the managerial roles of school principals. The school administrator-respondents obtained a grand weighted mean of 3.63, while the teacher-respondents obtained 3.65, which were both verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree. Significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents as regards the managerial roles of school principals. There is no significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents as regards the managerial roles of school principals except in the aspect of teamwork. School performance rating during the school year 2022-2023. The school performance rating achieved was 4.31 which was given an adjectival rating of Very Satisfactory. Significant relationship between the managerial roles of the principals and the school performance. There is no significant relationship between the managerial roles of the principals and the school's performance.

Keywords: *training, management, principal, managerial,*

Introduction

The school as a learning institution should create a conducive learning environment where students can acquire both academic and social skills, which are important to produce students with potential parallel to the government's mission in developing human resources as a prerequisite to the development of the knowledge-based economy. Certainly, it is said that a good leader carries out what is best for his or her school.

The managerial skills bestowed upon leaders, such as conceptual skills, human skills, technical skills, political skills, and decision-making skills, are important factors that contribute to the success of every school. An effective leader influences a variety of school outcomes, including student achievement, through their recruitment and motivation of quality teachers, their ability to identify and articulate school vision and goals, their effective allocation of resources, and their development of organizational structures to support instruction and learning" (Hornig et al, 2019).

Also, according to Lamas (2019) for instance contends that school performance is an issue that deeply concerns students, parents, teachers, and authorities in almost all parts of the globe. In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) is always alarmed by the country's basic education scenarios right now. Many reforms have been made to help improve the quality of education, but as observed, the scenarios seem to be almost the same.

Furthermore, the main duties of the school managers are to develop the learning environment at school and to ensure the development of teaching methods for teachers by determining the teacher's development, the educational goals of the school, directing educational applications to achieve educational objectives, making recommendations to find solutions for the problems, ensuring the motivation of teachers to improve the quality of education, maintaining discipline in the school environment.

Considering the above-mentioned ideas, the researcher was encouraged to conduct this study on the public elementary school principals' managerial roles and their effect on school performance to determine the various managerial roles and functions being performed by the school administrators; to determine if the school administrators are able to manage effectively and efficiently their identified roles in the school; and to determine if the school administrators' performance of their managerial roles have a great impact on the improvement of school performance.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the principals' managerial roles as correlates to school performance which served as basis for an enhanced management training workshop during the school year 2023-2024. More specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the perception of the school administrators and teachers on the managerial roles of school principals in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. healthy school culture;
 - 1.2. teamwork;
 - 1.3. communication;
 - 1.4. modification of practices and school structures;

- 1.5. curriculum leadership opportunities; and
- 1.6. good principal-staff relationships?
2. Is there a significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents as regards the managerial roles of school principals with respect to the above-cited aspects?
3. What is the school performance rating during the school year 2022-2023?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the managerial roles of the principals and the school performance?
5. What enhanced management training workshop may be proposed based on the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The research method used in the study is the descriptive type. Robson (2018) portrays an accurate profile of persons, events, or situations.

It also defines questions, people surveyed, and the method of analysis prior to the beginning of data collection. In other words, who, where, when, why, and sometimes how aspects of the research are defined.

The data will be collected from at least a part of the population as the basis for assessing the incidence, distribution, and interrelations of phenomena and variables as they occur in people's lives.

It concerns with the condition or relationship that exists. Opinions are held about processes that are going on, effects that are evident, or trends that are developing. It is primarily concerned with the present, although it often considers past events and influences related to conditions.

The researcher, therefore, would be able to describe the public elementary school principals' managerial roles and their effect on school performance from the survey, which made the design appropriate for the study.

Respondents

The researcher used purposive sampling. This was conducted in the Libmanan South district, Division of Camarines Sur. The respondents of the study were composed of Teachers and School Administrators.

Instrument

A questionnaire was used as an instrument for the data collection. Likert scale was used in this research study. It is a rating scale used to measure opinions, attitudes, or behaviors. It consists of a statement or a question, followed by a series of five statements. The respondents chose the option that best corresponds with how they feel about the statement or question.

Procedure

Permission from the concerned authorities was sought before the conduct of the study. Upon approval of the schools division superintendent and the principal, the questionnaire – checklists were administered to the school administrator and teacher-respondents of the selected public elementary schools in Libmanan South district, Division of Camarines Sur and were personally retrieved by the researcher.

Data Analysis

Frequency and Percentage Distribution. This was used to analyze and summarize the results of the responses from the questionnaire.

t-test. This was used to find out if there is a significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents as regards the managerial roles of school principals with respect to the above-cited aspects.

Pearson r Correlation. This was used to find out if there is a significant relationship between the managerial roles of the public elementary school principals and the school performance.

Ethical Considerations

This study shall protect the privacy of the respondent and shall not in any means expose confidential information.

Results and Discussion

As shown on Table 1, the administrator-respondents got an average weighted mean of 3.70, while the teacher-respondents got 3.66 which were both verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree.

This simply implies that school principals are able to manage the school properly through the implementation of various programs, good practices and in both teaching and learning which generally result to a healthy school environment.

It further shows that the school principals are taking full responsibility in performing their roles especially in capacitating and

empowering teachers, and these point are evidently seen on the responses of the two groups of respondents.

Table 1. Respondents' Perceptions on the Managerial Roles of School Principals in Terms of Healthy School Culture

Healthy School Culture	Administrators			Teachers		
	WM	SD	VI	WM	SD	VI
1. promote healthy relationship among teachers, parents, and external stakeholders.	3.70	0.459	SA	3.71	0.453	SA
2. address school safety issues and concerns.	3.70	0.462	SA	3.67	0.472	SA
3. implement behavior management practices strategies through positive ways.	3.70	0.462	SA	3.68	0.467	SA
4. capacitate teachers on how to resolve conflict, school violence, and prevent bullying incidents.	3.85	0.357	SA	3.64	0.482	SA
5. design and implement programs that can help increase students' interest in learning, improve academic outcomes, and reduce problematic and risky behavior.	3.55	0.500	SA	3.59	0.493	SA
Average Weighted Mean		3.70	SA	3.66	SA	
Standard Deviation		0.448		0.473		

Note: 1.00 – 1.75 (SD); 1.76 – 2.50 (D); 2.51 – 3.25 (A); 3.26 – 4.00 (SA)

As shown on Table 2, the teacher-respondents obtained an average weighted mean of 3.61, while the administrator-respondents obtained 3.68 which were both verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree.

Table 2. Respondents' Perceptions on the Managerial Roles of School Principals in Terms of Teamwork

Teamwork	Administrators			Teachers		
	WM	SD	VI	WM	SD	VI
1. encourage collaboration among teachers and other staff in the school.	3.63	0.484	SA	3.62	0.486	SA
2. practice a no-blame problem-solving approach.	3.66	0.476	SA	3.61	0.489	SA
3. create an environment where teachers and staff are open to raise comments and suggestions.	3.79	0.406	SA	3.65	0.476	SA
4. empower and urge teachers to cooperate with various programs and projects implemented in the school.	3.69	0.465	SA	3.58	0.495	SA
5. establish a schedule of regular meetings with the community partners to discuss progress regarding the implemented programs and projects.	3.65	0.480	SA	3.60	0.490	SA
Average Weighted Mean		3.68	SA	3.61	SA	
Standard Deviation		0.462		0.487		

Note: 1.00 – 1.75 (SD); 1.76 – 2.50 (D); 2.51 – 3.25 (A); 3.26 – 4.00 (SA)

This explains that in terms of teamwork, the school principals can demonstrate managerial actions specifically collaborative techniques that would encourage teachers and other employees to work as one in performing certain roles and in achieving various set goals.

Table 3. Respondents' Perceptions on the Managerial Roles of School Principals in Terms of Communication

Communication	Administrators			Teachers		
	WM	SD	VI	WM	SD	VI
1. collaborate with the teachers, staff, students, parents, and stakeholders to set goals, make decisions, and implement changes.	3.50	0.502	SA	3.62	0.486	SA
2. develop a shared vision and action for the school.	3.52	0.501	SA	3.65	0.478	SA
3. share resources and best practices that are aligned with the set goals and policies of the school.	3.67	0.471	SA	3.62	0.486	SA
4. provide opportunities and spaces for communication and collaborate to identify what has been achieved and what needs to be strengthened with the goals and policies made.	3.71	0.456	SA	3.65	0.477	SA
5. create professional learning communities, student clubs, and parent councils that foster dialogues and cooperation which in deeper sense intensify proper communication and understanding of the policies, goals, and procedures of the school.	3.71	0.456	SA	3.68	0.466	SA
Average Weighted Mean		3.62	SA	3.64	SA	
Standard Deviation		0.477		0.479		

Note: 1.00 – 1.75 (SD); 1.76 – 2.50 (D); 2.51 – 3.25 (A); 3.26 – 4.00 (SA)

As displayed on Table 3, the two groups of respondents achieved the average weighted means of 3.62 and 3.64 respectively. Both the computed average weighted means were verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree.

This elaborates that there is a firm action demonstrated by the school principals in promoting significant things and other factors that would lead to effective communication with the teachers, parents, and external stakeholders.

It also implies that the school principals are well-driven with their aims of developing and helping the school improve its practices through effective communication among others.

Table 4. Respondents' Perceptions on the Managerial Roles of School Principals in Terms of Modification of Practices and School Structures

Modification of Practices and School Structures	Administrators			Teachers		
	WM	SD	VI	WM	SD	VI
1. conduct observations / monitoring to see if teachers are holding up the policies implemented.	3.71	0.456	SA	3.66	0.474	SA
2. strengthen school practices and policies to better shape students' development and well-being.	3.55	0.499	SA	3.64	0.480	SA
3. identify any overlapping factors with the existing policies and practices.	3.38	0.486	SA	3.75	0.434	SA
4. create conditions that are fair and can help avoid problems and misunderstandings.	3.67	0.471	SA	3.60	0.491	SA
5. define and explain a parameter around which the school operates and influence the behavior of people to a particular outcome.	3.68	0.468	SA	3.61	0.488	SA
Average Weighted Mean	3.60		SA	3.65		SA
Standard Deviation	0.476			0.473		

Note: 1.00 – 1.75 (SD); 1.76 – 2.50 (D); 2.51 – 3.25 (A); 3.26 – 4.00 (SA)

As revealed on Table 4, the administrator-respondents got an average weighted mean of 3.60, while the teacher-respondents got 3.65 which were both verbally interpreted as Strong Agree.

This elucidates that the point of modifying practices and school structures have been performed or fulfilled by the school principals. With the high perceptions of the two groups of respondents, these clearly connote that there is a responsible management of observations and improvement process being done to strengthen policies, practices, conditions and to name a few. Thus, modification of practices and school structures is certainly shown.

Table 5. Respondents' Perceptions on the Managerial Roles of School Principals in Terms of Curriculum Leadership Opportunities

Curriculum Leadership Opportunities	Administrators			Teachers		
	WM	SD	VI	WM	SD	VI
1. set up / institutionalize teaching seminar in each learning area in every grade.	3.61	0.490	SA	3.68	0.469	SA
2. ascertain teaching program's goals in each learning area.	3.62	0.488	SA	3.68	0.467	SA
3. guide members in each learning area to design curriculum programs and teaching schedule and progress under the premise of respecting the teachers' opinions.	3.78	0.416	SA	3.71	0.454	SA
4. publish curriculum plan, discussion, and communication to foster program's trials and modification in each learning area.	3.66	0.476	SA	3.74	0.437	SA
5. process an effective educational personnel's training to cultivate the teachers' knowledge and skills.	3.55	0.499	SA	3.67	0.472	SA
Average Weighted Mean	3.64		SA	3.70		SA
Standard Deviation	0.474			0.460		

Note: 1.00 – 1.75 (SD); 1.76 – 2.50 (D); 2.51 – 3.25 (A); 3.26 – 4.00 (SA)

As seen on Table 5, the teacher-respondents obtained an average weighted mean of 3.70, while the administrator-respondents obtained 3.64 which were given a verbal interpretation of Strongly Agree.

This simply means that the school principals can effectively provide curriculum leadership opportunities for teachers through institutionalizing seminar-workshop that would benefit the teachers particularly in the improvement of their understanding as regards the curriculum contents and concepts that need to be understood specially in the design of curriculum plan.

In addition, the two groups of respondents are very amenable that the school principals are completely responsive to the demands or needs of teachers as far as curriculum leadership opportunities is concerned.

Table 6. Respondents' Perceptions on the Managerial Roles of School Principals in Terms of Good Principal-Staff Relationship

Good Principal-Staff Relationship	Administrators			Teachers		
	WM	SD	VI	WM	SD	VI
1. coordinate work within and across teams to facilitate collective efforts.	3.40	0.491	SA	3.62	0.486	SA
2. make sure that solutions are shared and applied school-wide.	3.74	0.442	SA	3.62	0.486	SA
3. coordinate the work of teachers and school-staff around shared goals.	3.71	0.456	SA	3.76	0.429	SA
4. create a strong learning climate by supporting teacher-leadership around school-wide goals.	3.55	0.499	SA	3.73	0.447	SA
5. develop plans and systems for supporting teachers to support students.	3.38	0.486	SA	3.61	0.488	SA
Average Weighted Mean	3.56		SA	3.67		SA
Standard Deviation	0.475			0.467		

Note: 1.00 – 1.75 (SD); 1.76 – 2.50 (D); 2.51 – 3.25 (A); 3.26 – 4.00 (SA)

As shown on Table 6, the administrator-respondents got an average weighted mean of 3.56, while the teacher-respondents got 3.67 which were both verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree.

This implies that the two groups of respondents have seen that there is a good relationship between the principals and the staff, and this can be seen through the high level of perception shown by the respondents. Also, with the high perceptions of the two groups of respondents, it also means that school principals are considering the involvement of teachers in creating an environment that is good which lead towards the achievement of goals and in achieving the set parameters of good principal-staff relationship.

Table 7. *Summary of Respondents' Perceptions on the Managerial Roles of School Principals*

Variables	Administrators		Teachers	
	AWM	VI	AWM	VI
a. Healthy School Culture	3.70	SA	3.66	SA
b. Teamwork	3.68	SA	3.61	SA
c. Communication	3.62	SA	3.64	SA
d. Modification of Practices and School Structures	3.60	SA	3.65	SA
e. Curriculum Leadership Opportunities	3.64	SA	3.69	SA
f. Good-Principal Staff Relationship	3.55	SA	3.67	SA
Grand Weighted Mean	3.63	SA	3.65	SA

As revealed on Table 7, the principal-respondents achieved a grand weighted mean of 3.63, while the teacher-respondents achieved 3.65. Both the computed grand weighted means were given a descriptive verbal interpretation of Strongly Agree.

This means that there is a similar perception of the two groups of respondents. It further explains that the managerial roles of public-school elementary principals are highly recognized and accepted by the two groups of respondents.

Table 8. *Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Two Groups As Regards the Managerial Roles of School Principals in Terms of Healthy School Culture*

Respondents	Mean	Standard Deviation	Computed t Value	Critical t Value $\alpha = 0.05$	Decision	Interpretation
School Administrators	3.70	0.448	0.960	2.78	Retain	Not Significant Ho
Teachers	3.66	0.473			Ho	

Note: Computed t value > Critical t value (Reject Ho) Computed t value < Critical t value (Retain Ho)

It could be gleaned on Table 8, in terms of healthy school culture, the computed t value of 0.960 is less than the computed critical t value of 2.78. At 0.05 level of significance, this led to the statistical decision of retaining the null hypothesis. This also indicates that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents.

This implies that the school administrators are very responsible in the implementation of programs projects, and other beneficial things that could promote a healthy school culture among teachers, staff, and other people.

Table 9. *Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Two Groups As Regards the Managerial Roles of School Principals in Terms of Teamwork*

Respondents	Mean	Standard Deviation	Computed t Value	Critical t Value $\alpha = 0.05$	Decision	Interpretation
School Administrators	3.68	0.462	3.087	2.78	Reject	Significant Ho
Teachers	3.61	0.487			Ho	

Note: Computed t value > Critical t value (Reject Ho) Computed t value < Critical t value (Retain Ho)

It can be observed on table 9, in terms of teamwork, the computed t value of 3.087 is higher than the critical t value of 2.78. At 0.05 level of significance, this resulted to the statistical decision of rejecting the null hypothesis. This also suggests that there is a significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents.

This clearly shows that there is still a need for the school principals to continue improving or strengthening their techniques and ways in encouraging teamwork among teachers and other staff.

Table 10. *Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Two Groups As Regards the Managerial Roles of School Principals in Terms of Communication*

Respondents	Mean	Standard Deviation	Computed t Value	Critical t Value $\alpha = 0.05$	Decision	Interpretation
School Administrators	3.62	0.477	-0.519	2.78	Retain	Not Significant Ho
Teachers	3.64	0.479			Ho	

Note: Computed t value > Critical t value (Reject Ho) Computed t value < Critical t value (Retain Ho)

As presented on Table 10, in terms of communication, the computed t value of -0.519 is less than the critical t value of 2.78. At 0.05 level of significance, this gives the statistical decision of retaining the null hypothesis. This also indicates that there is no significant

difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents.

This means that the perspective in the aspect of communication is given importance by the school principals. It further explains that the school principals are really up into improving or strengthening their abilities in communicating various information to all concerned personnel in the school and even to the external stakeholders.

Table 11. *Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Two Groups As Regards the Managerial Roles of School Principals in Terms of Modification of Practices and School Structures*

Respondents	Mean	Standard Deviation	Computed t Value	Critical t Value $\alpha = 0.05$	Decision	Interpretation
School Administrators	3.60	0.476	-0.639	2.78	Retain Ho	Not Significant
Teachers	3.65	0.473				

Note: Computed t value > Critical t value (Reject Ho) Computed t value < Critical t value (Retain Ho)

It can be seen on Table 11, in terms of modification of practices and school structures, the computed t value of -0.639 is less than the critical t value of 2.78. At 0.05 level of significance, this led to the statistical decision of retaining the null hypothesis. This also suggests that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents. This explains that the school principals have shown firmness and responsibility in the modification of practices and school structures, which certainly benefits the entire school organization.

Table 12. *Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Two Groups As Regards the Managerial Roles of School Principals in Terms of Curriculum Leadership Opportunities*

Respondents	Mean	Standard Deviation	Computed t Value	Critical t Value $\alpha = 0.05$	Decision	Interpretation
School Administrators	3.64	0.474	-1.617	2.78	Retain Ho	Not Significant
Teachers	3.70	0.460				

Note: Computed t value > Critical t value (Reject Ho) Computed t value < Critical t value (Retain Ho)

It can be observed on Table 12, in terms of curriculum leadership opportunities, the computed t value of -1.617 is less than the critical t value of 2.78. At 0.05 level of significance, this gives the statistical decision of retaining the null hypothesis. It also presents the idea that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents. This connotes that the school principals have properly managed the concepts on how to provide and strengthen curriculum leadership opportunities for teachers.

Table 13. *Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Two Groups As Regards the Managerial Roles of School Principals in Terms of Good Principal-Staff Relationships*

Respondents	Mean	Standard Deviation	Computed t Value	Critical t Value $\alpha = 0.05$	Decision	Interpretation
School Administrators	3.56	0.475	-1.690	2.78	Retain Ho	Not Significant
Teachers	3.67	0.467				

Note: Computed t value > Critical t value (Reject Ho) Computed t value < Critical t value (Retain Ho)

It can be seen on Table 13, in terms of good principal-staff relationships, the computed t value of -1.690 is less than the computed critical t value of 2.78. At 0.05 level of significance, the statistical decision is to retain the null hypothesis. This also indicates that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents. This implies that there is a clear manifestation that the school principals can manage the teachers specifically in the aspects of attitude at work and behavior towards colleagues, and this is evidently shown through the idea of being able to provide healthy working relationship, as seen also on the average responses of the two groups of respondents.

Table 14. *Summary of Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Managerial Roles Of School Principals*

Variables	Respondents	Computed t Value	Critical t Value $\alpha = 0.05$	Decision	Interpretation
a. Healthy School Culture	Administrators	0.960	2.78	Retain Ho	Not Significant
	Teachers				
b. Teamwork	Administrators	3.087	2.78	Reject Ho	Significant
	Teachers				
c. Communication	Administrators			Retain Ho	Not Significant
	Teachers	-0.519	2.78		
d. Modification of practices and school structures	Administrators	-0.639		Retain Ho	Not Significant
	Teachers		2.78		
e. Curriculum leadership opportunities	Administrators			Retain Ho	Not Significant
	Teachers	-1.617	2.78		
f. Good Principal-Staff Relationship	Administrators			Retain Ho	Not Significant
	Teachers	-1.690	2.78		

It could be gleaned on Table 14, in terms of healthy school culture, communication, modification of practices and school structures, curriculum leadership opportunities, and good principal-staff relationships, the computed t values of 0.960, -0.519, -0.639, -1.617, and -1.690 are less than the critical t value of 2.78. At 0.05 level of significance, this resulted to the statistical decision of retaining the null hypothesis.

However, in terms of teamwork, the computed t value of 3.087 is higher than the critical t value 2.78. At 0.05 level of significance, this led to the statistical decision of rejecting the null hypothesis. This also indicates that there is a significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents.

This generally means that among the variables considered under managerial roles, the school principals need to focus more and strengthen their skills in the aspect of teamwork.

Office Performance Commitment Review Form Rating (OPCRF)

Table 15. *Office Performance Commitment Review Form Rating (OPCRF for SY 2022-2023)*

Range	Numerical Rating	Adjectival Rating
4.500 - 5.000	4.31	Outstanding
3.500 - 4.499		Very Satisfactory
2.500 - 3.499		Satisfactory
1.500 - 2.499		Unsatisfactory
Below 1.499		Poor

As presented on Table 15, in terms of the office performance commitment and review form rating during the school year 2022-2023, the school achieved a performance rating of 4.31 which was given an adjectival rating of Very Satisfactory.

Test on Significant Correlation between OPCRF/School Performance and Managerial Roles of School Principals

Table 16. *Test on Significant Correlation between OPCRF/School Performance and Managerial Roles of School Principals*

Sources	OPCRF and Managerial Roles of School Principals				
	r - value	r ²	Strength of Relationship	Decision	VI
OPCRF versus Healthy School Culture	0.052	0.003	Very Low Correlation	Retain Ho	Not Significant
OPCRF versus Teamwork	0.000	0	No Correlation	Retain Ho	Not Significant
OPCRF versus Communication	0.015	0.000	Very Low Correlation	Retain Ho	Not Significant
OPCRF versus Modification of practices and school structures	0.030	0.001	Very Low Correlation	Retain Ho	Not Significant
OPCRF versus Curriculum leadership opportunities	0.038	0.001	Very Low Correlation	Retain Ho	Not Significant
OPCRF versus Good principal-staff relationship	0.101	0.010	Very Low Correlation	Retain Ho	Not Significant

Critical value of r: 0.05

As presented on Table 16, in terms of healthy school structure, communication, modification of practices and school structures, curriculum leadership opportunities, and good principal-staff relationships, the computed r- values of 0.052, 0.015, 0.030, 0.038, and 0.101, with the computed r² of 0.003, 0.000, 0.001, 0.001 and 0.010 indicates Very low correlation in the OPCRF. This also suggests the statistical decision of retaining the null hypothesis. It also explains that there is no significant correlation among the aforementioned variables on the OPCRF. And in terms of teamwork, with the computed r- value of 0.000 and r² of 0, it shows no correlation. This also gives the statistical decision of retaining the null hypothesis. It also indicates that there is no significant correlation between teamwork and OPCRF.

This generally implies that the managerial roles of public elementary school principals do not significantly affect the Office Performance Commitment and Review Form rating.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

The two groups of respondents have a high level of perceptions regarding the managerial roles of the school principals.

Both the teacher and the school administrator-respondents are amenable enough that the school principals are responsible in the performance of their duties. In addition, the two groups of respondents have also extended a strong agreement regarding the set indicators under the principals' managerial roles.

The managerial roles of the school principals do not significantly affect the school performance.

The following recommendations are hereby given:

The teachers may conduct brainstorming and Focus Group Discussion to discuss important matters on how to help the school principals

to strengthen more their management skills.

The teachers may collaborate with their school principals to suggest relevant ideas that could help in the smooth and effective management of the school in various aspects.

Future researchers may conduct similar study regarding the managerial roles of school principals using other variables.

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